

THE MODEL OF HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT FOR HOTEL BUSINESS TO PROMOTE TOURISM AND INVESTMENT IN THE MEKONG RIVER SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE

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Abstract

Aim: This research aims to study components of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone in order to set up and evaluate the model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone. **Methodology:** The Sample group of this research consists of 3 parts: 1(400 hotel executives, job leaders and staffs, 2(5 specialists for considering the suitability of model drafts, and 3(25 academicians, job leaders and staffs for evaluating possibilities of model application in human resource development for hotel business. Questionnaire was used for collecting information. Statistics used in this research consists of 1(frequency, 2(percentage, 3(mean, 4(Standard Deviation, 5(Factor Analysis, and 6(Canonical Analysis. **Finding:** The research results show that 1(The components of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consist of 2 parts: the first part is significant attributes of human resource for hotel business which are - interaction and communication ability, - services, - role awareness and the second part is human resource development process for hotel business which are - operational knowledge and - coaching. 2(Model of human resource development for hotel business consists of major components which are - attributes of human resource for hotel business and - human resource development process of hotel business. 3(Model assessed results of human resource development for hotel business, possibilities of using major and minor components, methods, activities, and indicators for enhancing attributes of human resource and its development process are in high level. **Conclusion:** Human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consists of 5 main components and 30 sub-components.

Keywords: Model, Human resource development, tourism and investment, Mekong River Special Economic Zone

INTRODUCTION

In the twelfth national economic and social development plan)2017 – 2021(, the government has directed tourism industry to be one of the strategies enhancing business competitiveness to creative business potential, encouraging the use of new technologies and bodies of knowledge in developing goods and services, potential investment throughout enabling supporting free trade by developing investment basis in accordance with lifestyle, culture, natural resources)National Economic and Social Development Board, 2016(. Thailand has determined special economic zones in different regions which are border facilitating trade and investment. Special Economic Zone)SEZ(is an industrial and commercial area with some conditions and privileges which are different from general business operations and beneficial to national development and investment promotion. Hotel business is the significant and necessary initiation for supporting tourism and investment in special economic zone which competes in

service quality to meet customer's demand. Hotel business can be succeeded by every level of hotel staffs who are fully and continuously developed for efficiency and effectiveness of excellent services for customers)Baud-Bovey, and Lawson, 1998(.

While the nation is promoting tourism and investment in special economic zone, problems in hotel business management in order to support tourism and investment in the 1st phase of the Mekong River Special Economic Zones consisting of 1(Nakorn Panom, 2(Sakon Nakorn and 3(Mukdaharn provinces which will support the expansion of tourism and investment must be urgently solved especially in human resource development and management. Jira Hongladarom)referred in Charnchote Chompunut, 2017(indicates overall systematic problems of industrial business in the aspect of hotel business management and human resource development like why foreigners get top and middle executive positions and higher salary than Thais, how educational institutes can produce suitable students for required hotel job positions, how hotel owners should invest in human resource, how hotel staffs should be developed or learn more to be talented executives earning suitable pay, how the hotels managed by Thais are able to compete and earn more income like hotels run by Chine's model, and how hotel staffs can have secured jobs and earn enough income for their lives and families.

Therefore, human resource development for hotel business becomes the topic that needs to be studied to urgently solve problems because hotel business is specific and sensitive by depending on one's society and it needs personal specific ability, intelligence, responsibility and staff's serious performance)Nolan, 2002(. Human resource on this service requires specific qualifications which are different from other businesses such as service mind, patience, being considerate including specific knowledge and skills)Chokanatakul, 2009(. Moreover, hotel business should provide staffs short and long-term training courses to enhance their work field knowledge; language skill, good services and application of information technology)Taweecheep, Keerativinikul & Jatuchai, 2011(. The researcher is therefore interested in studying human resource development for hotel business to set up the models to long-term promote and strengthen tourism and investment in special economic zone accordingly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Human Resource Development

Wexley & Latham)1991 p.224(mentioned the concept of human resource development that there are 3 major objectives:)1(to improve level of self-recognition,)2(to enhance individual work skills, and)3(to increase individual inspiration. To achieve these objectives, significant strategies are required;

1. Problem focusing is strategies emphasizing on reinforcement of individual concept, understanding, and knowledge. For example, the new-entry's pre-orientation is arranged to provide information regarding to work schedule, discipline, payment, holidays, leaves, welfare and other benefits. Moreover, the strategy also focuses on intellect which can be provided in form of human resource development in order to reinforce various aspects of knowledge such as leadership, friendship, or career progress development etc.

2. Behavior focusing is strategies emphasizing on changes of individual work behaviors such as behavioral expression which trainees will be observed and admired, actions in different situations and practices for following the observed pattern. Therefore, behavioral expression can be applied in individual development like job leader's commanding and management or communication skills etc.

3. Environment focusing is strategies emphasizing on improvement and development of individual work behaviors by changing work environment, for example, job rotation which employees can learn from different departments etc. In addition, environment might be changed by systematically setting up behavioral adjustment plan like rewarding or supporting system for those who work well etc.

Objectives of Human Resource Development

Swanson & Holton (2001 p.132) said that there are 2 major objectives of human resource development; 1) Individual and Organizational Learning, and 2) Individual and Organizational Performance

Pace, Smith & Mills (1991 p.76) described objectives of human resource development as follows:

1. Individual Development-ID is to help staffs know their strengths and weaknesses which will be improved and enhanced respectively by using various methods so that they can work on their full capacity or potential in human resource development activities in order to achieve individual together with organizational goals.

2. Organization Development-OD is to modify structures, roles and relationships in organizational systems so that the organizational operation pattern will be in accordance and updated to internal and external always-changing situations. This modification will help the organization survive and provide good work efficiency.

3. Career Development-CD is to allocate appropriateness between people and jobs in the organization. Therefore, a career development consultant plays a vital role in providing power of success in career development of human resource in the organization. It is considered helping an individual to find himself in his own world.

Principle of Human Resource Development

Pace, Smith & Mills)1991 p.82(described about personnel development process which enhances organizational personnel's knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes and increases individual work efficiency and organizational effectiveness. Therefore, human resource development is currently significant and needed for organizational development which has been more focused by many organizations.

Pace, Smith and Mills have proposed 7 significances and necessities of human resource development as follows:

1. Worth of the Individual: Organizations must give priority and recognize their staffs' values. The more their values are realized, the better the organizational effectiveness is.

2. **Employees as Resource:** It means that people should not be judged by their different works status, though, a working individual certainly plays a vital role in leading the organization to achieve goals. Therefore, human resource should be trained and developed for new working skills, knowledge and concepts including preparation for job promotion.
3. **Quality Work Environment:** This will help staffs work in clean and safe environment. When they are satisfied with their workplaces, they will be happy and intend to work as well.
4. **Employee Satisfaction:** Consideration of staff's satisfaction by setting up or maintaining their levels of satisfaction can be carried out by redesigning jobs in order to have appropriate and inspiring work performance.
5. **Continuous Learning Need:** Due to lack of the most complete knowledge and work skills, the new-entry might have to learn some required knowledge or skills so that they can continuously perform their jobs especially when there are changes, organizations must update their knowledge or be able to support them timely and appropriately.
6. **Change Opportunity Preparation:** As external situations have changed all the time, organizations need staffs who have different knowledge, skills and abilities. Therefore, staffs in organizations must prepare for changes of work patterns.
7. **Board Scope of HRD Concerns:** Human resource development is not only limited to personnel training or expertise improvement, but also expanded to understandings of human behaviors in various aspects such as motivating staffs in organizations to interact and respond to one another.

METHODOLOGY

1. This study is the mix of quantitative and qualitative research. Survey research was used in the former by collecting quantitative information from sample groups; 400 executives, job leaders and practitioner staffs of hotels in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone while qualitative research was carried out by collecting information from 2 sections; 1(5 specialists for considering the suitability of model drafts, and 2(25 experts and specialists for evaluating possibilities of model application in human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone.

2. Questionnaire, as a research tool, was used for collecting information whose 2 types of tool quality were approved before using in actual data collection and are described as follows:

2.1 Validity is verified by using Item Objective Congruence Index – IOC of questionnaire with studied contents. IOC scores are given by the experts using the determination of congruence index of contents in the questionnaire)Mehrens & Lehmann, 1991(.

2.2 Reliability: Questionnaire is tried out for reliability by using Cronbach's alpha coefficient) α (with 30 samples. Calculated result shows that the tool reliability equals to 0.976. It implies that reliability of the used tool is so high that it can be used for collecting information.

3. Data analysis and statistics used in this research consist of percentage, mean, Standard Deviation, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (on observed values and Common Factor Analysis with Varimax Orthogonal Rotation. Canonical analysis was used for relationship analysis of components of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone between human resource attributes and development for hotel business. It is used for appropriately creating human resource development patterns for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone.

RESULTS

Research results from human resource development process for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone are summarized in accordance with research objectives as follows:

1. Results of components of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone

1.1 Components of human resource attributes for hotel business can be proposed with study results of its levels of significance as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Shows Levels Of Significance Of Components Of Human Resource Attributes For Hotel Business			
Components of human resource attributes for hotel business	\bar{X}	S.D.	Levels of Significance
1. Service	4.65	.432	Highest
2. Public minds	4.56	.429	Highest
3. Social skills	4.54	.452	Highest
4. Communication	4.56	.473	Highest
Overall	4.58	.394	Highest

According to Table 1, significance of overall and every-aspect components of human resource attributes for hotel business is in the highest level.

As shown in the analyzed results of human resource attributes for hotel business, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test value equals to 0.940 which shows that the information is relative and suitable for factor analysis. When the condition of major component analysis is determined with >1 of Eigenvalues, it is found that there are 3 aspects of human resource attributes for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone; 1(Communication and interaction abilities, 2(Services, and 3(Role awareness with the following Factor Loading values as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Shows Human Resource Attributes For Hotel Business In The Mekong River Special Economic Zone

Human resource attributes for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone	Component		
	1	2	3
1. Communication and interaction abilities			
1.1 Having intelligence of appropriate communication and making understandings with customers or clients	.794	.292	.158
1.2 Expressing intention of listening to client's information or questions for good atmosphere	.737	.296	.217
1.3 Expressing honor to clients by using appropriate voice with them and situations	.704	.271	.259
1.4 Having knowledge and understandings in service jobs which are able to clearly provide correct information	.685	.393	.164
1.5 Having correct communication abilities by always firstly asking client's requirement	.625	.177	.367
1.6 Having good caring and service-mind attitudes and behaviors to clients	.621	.137	.353
1.7 Having an ability of appropriate language usage to communicate with clients in each situation	.621	.353	.208
1.8 Having an ability of appropriate expression to different situations	.561	.346	.344
1.9 Having prioritization of customer's significance with good relationship	.511	.114	.502
1.10 Being enthusiastic in working without thinking of self-interest	.488	.373	.355
1.11 Having an ability to properly change expression behaviors to the others	.474	.381	.406
2. Services			
2.1 Being physically and mentally prepared for providing services	.266	.767	.173
2.2 Quick services	.193	.762	.248
2.3 Having an ability to analyze client's requirements	.252	.744	.237
2.4 Having an ability to provide impressive services to clients	.163	.726	.311
2.5 Providing services with smiles and happiness	.356	.701	.169
2.6 Providing services to customers or clients equally	.293	.660	.110
2.7 Being responsible and realizing one's duties on overall organization	.305	.527	.403
3. Role awareness			
3.1 Being generous to clients by considering their actual requirements	.111	.191	.774
3.2 Considering customers or clients' benefits from being provided services	.176	.371	.694
3.3 Realizing one's assigned roles and responsibilities	.385	.162	.642
3.4 Facilitating and providing information with willingness	.283	.283	.620
3.5 Having an ability to well coordinate and build relationship with colleagues	.429	.121	.603
3.6 Providing services as soon as customers require	.318	.313	.587

1.2 Components of human resource development process for hotel business can be proposed with study results of its levels of significance as shown in Table 3.

Human resource development process for hotel business	\bar{X}	SD.	Levels of Significance
1. Coaching	4.61	.458	Highest
2. Training	4.64	.380	Highest
3. Education	4.55	.463	Highest
4. Learning	4.56	.475	Highest
5. Work system	4.61	.456	Highest
Overall	4.59	.360	Highest

According to Table 3, significance of overall and every-aspect components of human resource development process for hotel business is in the highest level.

As shown in the analyzed results of human resource development process for hotel business, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test value equals to 0.939 which shows that the information is relative and suitable for factor analysis. When the condition of major component analysis is determined with >1 of Eigenvalues, it is found that there are 4 processes of human resource development for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone; 1(knowledge on work performance, 2(education and training, 3(coaching, and 4(personnel development encouragement with the following Factor Loading values as shown in Table 4.

Human resource development process for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone	Component			
	1	2	3	4
1. Learning on work performance				
1.1 Executives give opportunities for their personnel to express their opinions about changing new patterns of work methods.	.773	.168	.189	.060
1.2 Work system is prepared by describing complete procedures.	.731	.253	.169	.097
1.3 Quicker and more convenient work performance by applying technology with service provision to customers	.722	.216	.200	.040
1.4 Different types of rewards are prepared to inspire and give learning morale and encouragement from good work performance.	.693	.304	.119	.123
1.5 New body of knowledge from personnel best practice is provided.	.671	.351	.113	.096
1.6 Knowledge sharing is provided to create learning environment for personnel in organizations.	.660	.318	.177	-.043
1.7 Best practice is transferred or shared to lead to better work development and improvement	.659	.299	.208	.046
1.8 Masterpiece award competition is provided to encourage continuous performance development.	.636	.259	.167	.153
1.9 Encouraging personnel learning atmosphere for better work performance.	.636	.390	.072	.060
1.10 Supporting learning factors required for personnel work performance	.599	.367	.092	.011

Human resource development process for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone	Component			
	1	2	3	4
1.11 Human resource development plan required for personnel training is determined.	.464	.349	.005	.404
2. Education and training				
2.1 Executives give priority and recognize' values of human resource development on education.	.246	.741	.200	-.104
2.2 Personnel supportive policies for higher education are provided.	.371	.675	.042	-.003
2.3 Cooperating with educational institutes to provide education about human resource development in accordance with job employment	.339	.660	.176	-.038
2.4 Encouraging and developing education curriculum in accordance with career	.352	.627	.105	-.017
2.5 Regular training of new knowledge is provided so that personnel are aware of changes	.390	.605	.087	.267
2.6 Personnel training is determined to be a part of career progress	.322	.575	.081	.391
2.7 Implanting human resource development by using education as an important tool for human development	.440	.572	.106	-.006
2.8 When personnel are trained, knowledge sharing is regularly provided.	.334	.548	.103	.404
3. Coaching				
3.1 Searching for coaching-talented speakers to be job coaches	.049	.133	.803	.060
3.2 Executives give priority to coaching as it leads to correct work Performance	.195	.041	.790	.062
3.3 Educating benefits of job coaching	.112	.111	.786	.006
3.4 Raising awareness of values and significance of coaching for personnel's Understandings	.135	.036	.784	.087
3.5 Enhancing coaching atmosphere	.139	.153	.751	.043
3.6 Coaching policies are internally and clearly determined.	.192	.084	.696	.016
4. Personnel development encouragement				
4.1 Executives determine personnel development encouragement as a major organizational policy on personnel capabilities development and training.	-.020	-.100	.108	.726
4.2 New patterns of personnel capabilities development and training are continuously provided.	.452	.448	.115	.472

1.3 Canonical coefficient between human resource attributes and development process for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone equals to 0.858 which shows that the human resource attributes for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone unidirectionally and highly relates to the human resource development process as shown in the following table.

Table 5: Shows Canonical Coefficients And Relationship Between Human Resource Attributes And Development Process For Hotel Business To Promote Tourism And Investment In The Mekong River Special Economic Zone			
Canonical Coefficients	0.858*	0.336*	0.177
Human resource attributes for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone			
1. Communication and interaction abilities	0.679*	1.491	-0.521
2. Services	0.256*	-0.422	-1.411
3. Role awareness	0.147*	-1.327	-0.826
Human resource development process of hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone			
1. Learning on work performance	0.025*	1.247	-0.443
2. Education and training	0.145	-1.215*	-0.957*
3. Coaching	0.928*	0.203	0.303
4. Personnel development encouragement	0.004	-0.646*	1.022

P-value 0.05

According to the study results of components relating to human resource for hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone by wrapping up similar minor components together to become one, details are described in Table 6 and 7 as follows:

Table 6: Shows Components Of Human Resource Attributes For Hotel Business In The Mekong River Special Economic Zone	
Main components	Sub components
1. communication and interaction abilities	1(having intelligence of appropriate communication 2(listening to client's information and using appropriate languages 3) giving honor to clients and being enthusiastic in providing services 4(asking clients and providing correct information 5(Expressing appropriate behaviors 6(being aware of customer's significance
2. Services	1(being ready and providing quick services 2(analyzing client's requirements 3(impressing clients 4(providing services with smile 5(providing services with equity
3. Role awareness	1(role awareness 2(giving priority to clients 3(providing services with willingness 4(coordinating and building good relationship 5(in-time services

According to Table 6, there are 3 main and 16 sub components of significant attributes of human resource for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone.

Table 7: Shows Components Of Human Resource Development Process For Hotel Business In The Mekong River Special Economic Zone	
Main components	Sub components
1. Learning on work performance	1(enhancing learning from best practice 2(providing and improving work system 3(encouraging technology application in providing services 4(modifying work methods 5(sharing new knowledge from practices 6(sharing knowledge among personnel 7(continuous learning and development 8(building good work atmosphere 9(determining explicit personnel development plan
2. Coaching	1(searching for job coaches 2(giving priority to coaching 3(raising awareness of coaching 4(building coaching atmosphere 5(determining coaching policies

According to Table 7, there are 2 main and 14 sub-components of human resource development process for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone.

2. Results of building models of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone

Results of building models of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consisting of main components relating to human resource development are as follows:

2.1 Human resource attributes for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consist of 1(communication and interaction abilities, 2(services, and 3(role awareness.

2.2 Human resource development process of hotel business in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consists of 1(learning on work performance and 2(coaching.

The model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone can be proposed as described below.

Figure 1: The model of human resource development for hotel business to promote business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong river special economic zone

3. Assessed results of the model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone

The model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone is possible to be used for human resource development for hotel business in high level ($\bar{X}=4.12$). When each component is individually considered, communication and interaction abilities are found with the highest mean value ($\bar{X}=4.18$) followed by role awareness ($\bar{X}=4.14$) as shown in Table 8.

Possibilities for using human resource development for hotel business	Levels of Possibilities		
	\bar{X}	SD.	Meaning
1. Components of communication and interaction attributes	4.18	0.20	High
2. Components of service attributes	4.01	0.31	High
3. Components of role awareness attributes	4.14	0.27	High
Overall	4.12	0.22	High

According to Table 8, overall possibilities for using model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone is high level.

DISCUSSION

Research results on the model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone can be discussed in 3 sections according to research objectives as follows:

1. Studied results of components of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Zone can be summarized into 2 main sections as described below:

1.1 Significant human resource attributes for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Zone consist of 3 main components; 1(communication and interaction abilities, 2(services and 3(role awareness in order to encourage personnel to be enthusiastic and perform with their full capabilities to communicate information with customers or clients. As providing services that meet customers' demands is considered as significant human resource attribute for hotel business, executives or entrepreneurs therefore firstly give priority to personnel development so that customers will be confident in their business operation. This leads to the determination of fundamental principle of work standard development for personnel to achieve business goals which is in accordance with Wexley and Latham)1991(who described that to achieve goals of human resource development, different strategies are required; 1(cognition; strategies emphasizing on reinforcement of individual concept, understanding, and knowledge. For example, the new-entry's pre-orientation is arranged to provide information regarding to work schedule, discipline, payment, holidays, leaves, welfare and other benefits. 2(behavior; strategies emphasizing on changes of individual work behaviors such as behavioral expression which can be applied in individual development like communication or service provision etc.and 3(environment focusing; strategies emphasizing on improvement and development of individual work behaviors by changing work environment, for example, job rotation which employees can learn from different departments and be able to understand overall work system and provide information or services immediately leading to customers or clients' better satisfaction.

1.2 Human resource development process for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone consists of 2 main components; 1(learning on work performance and 2(coaching in order to encourage personnel to have better potential and capabilities. Therefore, organizations often determine such components as personnel development policy so that the personnel are always ready to work and immediately provide customers or clients services which is the reason why service business requires progressive personnel development by using different approaches to solve problems caused by lack of work skills. It is corresponding to concept on human resource development necessity described by Chalermpong Meesomnai)2010(who said that guidelines of human resource development by using human resource development techniques and approaches are "activities and procedures enhancing and developing appropriate

personnel knowledge, skills, and attitudes in organizations to be in accordance with their current and future responsibilities and roles so that they can be efficiently successful and give the highest effectiveness.” The aforementioned concept is also in accordance with Chotichawan Fukijkan’s concept)2013(proposing guidelines of human resource development consisting of training, education and development which all benefit self-developed personnel and the organizations.

2. Validity of results of building the model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone is in the highest level. However, when each assessed component is individually considered, the top 3 mean values are the component of service attribute which has the highest level of validity, followed by the component of role awareness attribute, as well as the comprehension of model components. The studied model can be used in service attribute development leading to better-quality service which is client’s expectation. This is in accordance with Schmenner’s concept)Schmenner, 1995(describing that service quality comes from actual perception which is subtracted by service expectation. Provided that clients perceive that the services they have are greater than what they have expected, service quality is therefore positive. Likewise, Love Lock)1996(thought that service quality is a concept about goods or services searched by potential customers and might be assessed before they are consumed. Zieldin)1996(proposed that service quality relates to clients’ expectation on quality after the service information is informed.

3. Assessed results of the model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone are highly possible to be used in human resource development. However, when each assessed component is individually considered especially the component of coaching development process, it is highly possible to be used in human resource development for hotel business as well as of learning on work performance. Being progressively developed via different approaches will enable personnel to be able to manage various problems. Therefore, the model application of personnel development for hotel business is not only standardizing personnel work performance, but also enabling them to provide over-expected services which will help solve better work problems. This is in accordance with the study of Wattana Thanongpaeng and Chawalee Na Talang)2017(who have studied on the model of small hotel business management. Research results relating to personnel development in organizational management are found that for the internal management, job description must be clearly identified while personnel growth and development must be prepared for business expansion. Practitioner-level personnel must always be developed in order to be able to solve problems efficiently and have skills and creativity by applying different innovations in their work performance leading to the establishment of practice-based knowledge which will be transferred and publicized to other personnel and becomes organizational significant knowledge. This is in accordance with the study of Duangamol Pongpankhae and Theerawat Chantuek)2018(who have researched on the development of hotel work system by using creative innovation to enhance health tourism in the future. Research results were found that main components of the study consist of 1(service 2(innovation 3(enhancement for creativity and 4(improvement of competencies to learning organizations.

CONCLUSION

The model of human resource development for hotel business to promote tourism and investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone from this research shows 2 parts of significant components; 1(important attributes of human resource for hotel business which are 1(communication and interaction abilities, 2(services, 3(role awareness and)2(human resource development process for hotel business which are 1(learning on work performance and 2(coaching. These components play vital roles in enhancing personnel capabilities and potential in hotel business to be internationally standardized and well prepared for tourism and business investment in the Mekong River Special Economic Zone as each component describes methods, process and guidelines that are applied in personnel development which is more completely in accordance with roles and duties. Moreover, personnel development indicators are also determined for assessing accomplishment directly gained from human resource development for hotel business.

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